

Estimation the Level of Mirna23a in Patients with Complicated and Non-Complicated Urinary Tract Infection

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Abstract

Objective: miRNAs, a small non-coding (20-25 nucleotide) RNA molecule, play a crucial role in controlling the host's defense mechanisms where their expression regulates the actions of the cells that protect the host from disease or inflammatory situations. It may serve as a significant biomarker for infectious diseases and is essential in the diagnosis of many other diseases. So that, this research aims to investigate the role of miRNA23a in progression of urinary tract infection.

Methods: A case-control study involved 116 patients with UTI and 36 healthy individuals. Urine specimens have been collected for direct culturing of *K. pneumoniae*, while blood specimens were collected for direct extraction of RNA. Vitek 2 compact system was used to confirm identification of *K. pneumoniae* and RT qPCR technique was followed up for detection the level of miRNA23a gene expression among patients and healthy group.

Results: out of 116 urine specimens only 13 isolates *K. pneumoniae* were detected according to the cultural properties while confirmed identification of *K. pneumoniae* by vitek 2 compact systems revealed only 7(6%) isolates were belonged to *K. pneumoniae*. The results of RT qPCR showed that the Ct value of miRNA23a in UTI patient range between 30.1-39.04 compared with healthy group (27.07-38.39) where an increase in the level of gene expression among UTI patients in comparison with healthy group (fold change for patients and healthy 13.01128 and 1 respectively). The fold change of miRNA in complicated UTI patients was 1.625879 compared with non-complicated UTI which was 7.074609178 which revealed to down regulation of miRNA in complicated UTI patients.

Conclusion: A correlation has been found between the level of miRNA23a gene expression and UTI in patients infected with *K. pneumoniae*.

Key words: *K. pneumoniae*, complicated UTI, miRNA23a, RT qPCR.

1. INTRODUCTION

MicroRNAs, a transcripts made from RNA, are small non-coding (20-25 nucleotide) RNA molecule which act as a regulatory factors of gene expression of biological processes such as immune modulation and gene expression [1]. They are widely distributed throughout the body, affecting the activities and functions of the kidney, liver, and lungs. The expression of miRNA regulates the actions of the cells that protect the host from disease or inflammatory situations, so that the change in the level of its gene expression may influence inflammation, differentiation, and cell proliferation which cause the development and progression of several medical problems, as well as the host's resistance to some diseases [2,3,4]. It is possible to

use these changed miRNA levels in human blood or serum during various pathogenic infections as a biomarker to distinguish between infectious diseases in humans [5].

MicroRNA is tissue- or even organ-specific and its expression is strictly regulated in cells [6]. Genetic polymorphisms, asymmetric miRNA strand selection, DNA methylation, and miRNA interactions with RNA-binding proteins or other RNAs are some of the factors that control miRNA expression and function [7]. It has been demonstrated that miRNAs influence both susceptibility to infections and acquired immune responses against infectious diseases. Furthermore, miRNAs have a unique function in controlling commensal bacteria, which in turn modifies barrier function and preserves intestinal homeostasis [8].

The microRNA-23a belongs to the miR-23-27-24 cluster but exists in different isoforms, which shows altered expression in various diseases [9]. Sometimes, the biological functions of miR-23, miR-27, and miR-24 are distinct despite sharing a common target site [10], this due to variations in expression regulation. Expression of microRNA-23a is regulated mainly by transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β) signaling [11]. Some studies have shown that abnormal expression levels of miR-23 enable it to serve as a potential biomarker for the diagnosis and progression of diseases such as metabolic and immune disorders [12]. This research aim to investigate the level of gene expression of miRNA32a in patient suffering from complicated UTI in Alnnajf Alashraf City.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Patients and Control Group

A case-control study was conducted in AL-Najaf AL-Ashraf Teaching Hospital and out patients of both sexes between July 2023 to the November 2023. A total of 116 patients suffering from Urinary Tract Infection (UTI) and complicated UTI (cUTI) were recurrent in the following study. UTI and cUTI patient were confirmed by pathological reports according to urologist. Also, 36 individuals with no signs or symptoms of UTI according to the clinical diagnosis and their urine gave negative results for culturing was included in present study as control group.

2.2. Specimens collection and Manipulation

Midstream urine specimen of all 116 patients were collected using sterile screw cap and cultured on blood agar and MacConkey agar for primary detection of *K. pneumonia* isolates. Blood specimens have been collected from patients whom showed positive results for *K. pneumonia* growth. Blood specimens were collected by puncture of the vein after decontamination of skin and transferred to gel tube for direct extraction of RNA for molecular detection of microRNA by Real-time PCR.

2.3. Total RNA extraction Kit

TransZol RNA extraction kit (TRANS,China) has been used for extraction of RNA from serum specimens of both patients and control groups.

2.4. RT-qPCR Master Mix

GoTaq 1-Step RT-qPCR System combines GoScrip Reverse Transcriptase and GoTaq qPCR Master Mix in a single-step real-time amplification reaction has been used (Promega, USA). The system, optimized for RT-qPCR, contains a proprietary fluorescent DNA binding dye and Sybr Green Dye.

2.5. The sequences of miRNA23a and U6 Primers

The sequences of primer used in this study were as followed: miRNA-23a F: 5'-CCA TGA ACT TTC TGC TCT TC-3' and miRNA-23a R: 5'-GGT GAG AGG TCT AGT TCC CGA-3' [13]; and U6F:5'-CTC GCT TCG GCA GCA CA-3' and U6R: 5'-AAC GCT TCA CGA ATT TGC GT-3' [14].

3. Testing Methods

3.1. Identification of *K. pneumoniae*

All suspected bacterial isolates that grow on MacConkey agar plates and gave pink mucoid colonies with lactose fermentation were further identified by Vitek 2 compact system using GNID card.

3.2. Detection of miRNA32a Level by Quantitative real time PCR method

3.2.1. Total RNA Extraction from Serum

Serum samples restored from liquid nitrogen and melt at room temperature, after complete melting, the sampled mixed well by vortex and RNA extraction carried out using TransZol RNA extraction kit according to the manufacturing recommendation. The purity and concentration of extracted RNA was measured by DNA-RNA Spectrophotometer (Bio-Droop, England).

3.2.2. RT-qPCR for Detection the Level of miRNA32a in Serum

One step RT-qPCR technique has been followed up. The RT-qPCR mixture with a final volume 20 μ l was prepared according to the manufacturer recommendation by mixing 10 μ l of 1X GoTaq® qPCR Master Mix, 0.4 μ l of 1X GoScript™ RT Mix for 1-Step RT qPCR, 0.6 μ l of each forward and reverse primer, 1.6 μ l of 25mM MgCl₂, 5 μ l of extracted RNA template, and 1.8 μ l of nuclease free water. Amplification was carried out using Real time PCR thermocycler (Analytika Jena, Germany) and the reaction conditions were set as follows: 37°C for 15 min for Reverse transcription, then 95°C for 10 min for RT inactivation/Hot-start activation followed by 40 cycles of 95°C for 30 sec, 55°C for 20 sec and 72°C for 30 sec. The gene expression (fold change) was calculated as follows: Fold Gene Expression RQ = 2^{- $\Delta\Delta$ CT}

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Prevalence of *K. pneumoniae* in Patients with UTI

According to the primary cultural properties and microscopic examination the results showed that out of 116 urine specimens cultured on MacConkey agar plates only 13 isolates were belonged to *K. pneumoniae*. The colonies appeared mucoid, large and pink due to lactose fermentation, whereas on blood agar they appeared large, white, mucoid colonies without hemolysis. The microscopic examination of bacterial cells showed Gram- negative, encapsulated, non- motile bacilli. The results of VITEK-2 System to confirmed identification of bacterial isolates showed that only 7(6%) isolates were belonged to *K. pneumoniae*.

The results also showed that 2 isolates were isolated from patients with complicated UTI, while 5 isolates were isolated from patients with non-complicated UTI, in addition to that the results show the largest number of isolates were isolated from age group 20-29 (42.85%) followed by age group 30-39 (28.57%) as mention in figure 1.

K. pneumoniae, as a member of the Enterobacteriaceae family, it is a significant pathogen in hospital and community environments [15]. Many studies showed different isolation ratio some of them were close to our study such as (4.03%, 7.6%), while other studies reported different percentages such as (24.6%, 35.9% and 81.4%) [16]. This different in the prevalence rates may be due to geographic location and population's hygiene behaviors [17].

Figure 1: Distribution of *K. pneumoniae* isolates among age groups

4.2. The level of Gene Expression of miRNA23a:

The results of RT qPCR for detection of miRNA-23a gene expression were mention in figure 2 where the Ct value of miRNA23a in UTI patient range between 30.1 - 39.04 compared with healthy group which was range between 27.07 - 38.39 (Figure 2). An increase in the level of gene expression among UTI patients in comparison with healthy group where the fold change for UTI patients and healthy group were 13.01128 and 1 respectively (Figure 3). Among complicated UTI patients the fold change of miRNA was 1.625879 compared with non-complicated UTI which was 7.074609178 which revealed to down regulation of miRNA in complicated UTI patients.

Figure 2: Real time RT-qPCR threshold curves for amplification of miRNA 23a in UTI patients

Also the results showed that the level of gene expression of miRNA23a in UTI patients infected with *K. pneumoniae* was down regulated (fold change=0.014579) compared with healthy group (fold change=1.0) as shown in figures 4.

Figure 3: The fold change difference of miRNA-23a between UTI patients and healthy group.

Figure 4: Fold change difference of miRNA-23a between patients infected with *K. pneumoniae* compared to healthy group.

There are more than 1,000 miRNAs have been discovered in the human genome and that one miRNAs can have hundreds of targets, Another layer of regulatory complexity by the fact that mRNAs are often can be regulated by multiple miRNAs[18]. It is known that miR-23a is highly stable across species and can control several disease processes, such as inflammation, immune regulation, and cancer[19, 29].

Host miRNA expression can be changed in response to various bacterial pathogens. As a mention in our results the level of gene expression of miRNA 23a was increased in patients infected with *K. pneumoniae* and suffering from UTI in comparison with control, this may suggest that host miRNAs act as an important in the molecular interplay between bacterial pathogens and host cells [21]. Many previous studies revealed that miRNA23a play a role in endo-lysosomal pathways of mycobacteria, and get upregulated in bovine alveolar macrophages in response to *M. bovis* infection [22]. Also, Lipoteichoic acid in *S. aureus* (LTA) stimulate the elevated of cellular miR-23a level, which disrupt inflammatory action by affecting PI3K, besides that, cell-derived exosomes are involved in the M1 polarization of bovine macrophages [23]. In contrast, the adhesion of *K. pneumoniae* was modulated by miR-23a that affects the integrin mediated $\alpha 5\beta 1$ signaling, where the expression level of miR-23a was downregulated in pulmonary epithelial cells with *K. pneumoniae*. The role of integrin $\alpha 5\beta 1$ was enhanced by miR-155, which then cause the increase of actin polymerization. Moreover, the expression levels of high mobility group nucleosomal-binding domain 2 (HMG2), which is affected by miR-155 and miR-23a, were take a role in adjust the $\alpha 5\beta 1$ expression and *K. pneumoniae* attaching, which explain a good relation between miRNAs and integrin function that can regulate bacterial adhesion [24, 25].

5. Conclusion

A correlation has been found between the level of miRNA23a gene expression and UTI in patients with complicated and non-complicated UTI as well as patients infected with *K. pneumoniae*, So that a research required evaluating the role of miRNA23a in regulation of immune response related to UTI.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interests.

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